

Ethical Leadership of the Teacher in Classroom Management

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Abstract

Classroom management is the continuation of the necessary opportunities and processes for the realization of learning, by providing the learning order, environment and rules. It can be said that the ability of students to be educated in the desired direction depends on the successful management of the classroom. Ethics is a discipline of moral principles theory and philosophy that strives to realize a certain ideal of living, questions the era and society in which it lives, offers alternative values instead of existing values, clearly defines life norms, in short, makes life meaningful. Leadership, on the other hand, is the process of influencing and directing the behavior and activities of others, without coercion, in order to set personal and group goals and achieve set goals, under certain conditions. In this study, which focuses on the ethical leadership role of the teacher in classroom management; First of all, the concept of classroom management and classroom management models are explained, and the basic elements of classroom management are discussed. Then, the concepts of ethics and leadership were defined, ethical leadership and the concept of ethical leadership in classroom management were discussed, and the power sources and characteristics of the teacher as an ethical leader were mentioned.

Keywords: Management, Educational management, Classroom management, Ethics, Leadership, Ethical leadership

Sınıf Yönetiminde Öğretmenin Etik Liderliği

Öz

Sınıf yönetimi; öğrenmenin gerçekleşmesi için gerekli olanak ve süreçlerin, öğrenme düzeninin, ortamının ve kurallarının sağlanarak sürdürülmesidir. Öğrencilerin istedik yönde eğitilebilmelerinin, sınıfın başarılı bir biçimde yönetilmesine bağlı olduğu söylenebilir. Etik, belli bir yaşama idealini hayata geçirebilmek için çabalayan, içinde yaşadığı çağı ve toplumu sorgulayan, var olan değerlerin yerine alternatif değerler sunan, yaşam normlarını açıkça tanımlayan, kısaca hayatı anlamlı kılan ahlaki ilkeler kuramı ve felsefe disiplini. Liderlik ise belirli şartlar altında, kişisel ve grup amaçlarını belirleme ve belirlenen amaçların gerçekleştirilmesi için, bir kimsenin başkalarının davranışlarını ve faaliyetlerini zorlama olmaksızın etkilemesi ve yönlendirmesi sürecidir. Sınıf yönetiminde öğretmenin etik liderlik rolünü konu alan bu çalışmada; öncelikle sınıf yönetimi kavramı ve sınıf yönetimi modelleri açıklanmış, sınıf yönetiminin temel öğeleri ele alınmıştır. Daha sonra, etik ve liderlik kavramları tanımlanmış, etik liderlik ve sınıf yönetiminde etik liderlik kavramı ele alınmış, etik lider olarak öğretmenin güç kaynaklarına ve özelliklerine değinilmiştir.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Yönetim, Eğitim yönetimi, Sınıf yönetimi, Etik, Liderlik, Etik Liderlik

Type: Research article	Sending Date: 11.04.2023	Acceptance Date: 29.08.2023
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To cite: Töngel, O., Eryaşar, E. & Eryaşar, C. (2023). Ethical leadership of the teacher in classroom management. *International Journal of Unique Glance at Education*, 1(2), 302-323. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8263905

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Introduction

Being the smallest unit of the education system, the classroom is a functional and special environment in which educational goals are transferred to one's behavior. In this sense, it can be said that the classroom environment is where dynamic processes interact. Classroom management is the management of life in the classroom in harmony like an orchestra, which includes elements such as organizing resources, arranging the environment effectively, observing student development, and anticipating problems that may arise. Classroom management is not a teaching system, but a systematic method that coordinates the inevitable diversity, multiculturalism, and complexity of the modern classroom (Tas & Minaz, 2021). An effective educational activity requires an appropriate classroom environment, a qualified teacher, an effective management, cooperation among the school, the student, and the parent, and an orderly classroom environment with mutually determined rules. All teachers need to have knowledge and skills in classroom management to ensure that such an environment is created.

The rapid transformation we are in has had great effects on education as in every field. By moving away from the classical definition of education, it is now defined as the process of making the child an active member of the universal structure, first himself and then the society in which he lives, within the scope of his individual characteristics and the environment, conditions and possibilities at hand (Toprakci, 2008). At this point, the duty of schools, which are the most important educational institutions, is of great importance. The fact that educational institutions can achieve a structure that is suitable for the development and change rhythm of the globalizing world will be possible by considering the smallest unit of the system, the classrooms (Caglar, 2010). The classroom is a secondary system of relationships in which educational activities take place after the family in students' lives.

Most of the time of students and teachers is spent in this common living area (Sadik, 2016). The classroom is the core center where teaching takes place, with the simplest definition. Classrooms under the roof of the school can be defined as environments where students and teachers come together and where teaching and learning activities take place. This short description also shows that the class itself has many qualities to be examined. The classroom is a special environment structured for the realization of educational goals with its unique character. The classroom is the most important environment in which the student interacts with the environment towards the learning goal under the guidance of the teacher (Gulec & Alkis, 2004).

Classroom management includes not only ensuring the discipline of the teacher, who is the classroom manager, but also ensuring the physical order of the classroom environment, arranging in-class communication, briefly providing a suitable environment for educational activities in the classroom (Seyfullahogullari, 2010). In addition, an effective classroom management affects not only teaching activities but also the development of students. The fact that how successful teachers are in teaching activities in the classroom largely depends on how competent they are in managing human problems shows that classroom management is a subject area that should be given more importance (Sadik, 2016). Managing the classroom does not mean that the teacher's authority is dominant in the classroom, but rather the creation of a classroom climate that enables learning (Tertemiz, 2006).

The smallest unit of the education system, the classroom, is a functional and special environment in which educational goals are transferred to the behavioral dimension. In this sense, it can be said that the classroom environment is an area where dynamic processes interact. classroom management; It is the management of the life in the classroom in harmony like an orchestra, which includes elements such as organizing resources, arranging the environment effectively, observing student development, predicting student problems that may arise. Classroom management is not a teaching system, but can be defined as a systematic method that coordinates the inevitable diversity, multiculturalism and complexity of the modern classroom.

Method

This study is a qualitative research designed in descriptive research model. Descriptive studies describe a given situation as precisely and carefully as possible (Buyukozturk, 2021). Qualitative research is a type of research in which qualitative data collection methods such as "observation, interview or document analysis" are used, and a qualitative process is followed to reveal facts and events in a realistic and holistic way in the natural environment (Yildirim & Simsek, 2021). In this study, document analysis method was used. Document review can be used as a stand-alone source of information that creates all the data, or it can also be used as an additional data source that contributes to the main data collection method (Mertkan, 2015). Written materials are considered as documents; photographs, pictures and videos also make up the documents (Guzel-Candan & Ergen, 2014).

In this research, data obtained from documents/resources were subjected to descriptive analysis. Descriptive analysis is based on the systematic and clear description of the data obtained within a predetermined plan (Yildirim & Simsek, 2021). In this study, which focuses on the ethical leadership role of the teacher in classroom management; first of all, the concept of classroom management and classroom management models are explained, and the basic elements of classroom management are discussed. Then, the concepts of ethics and leadership were defined, ethical leadership and the concept of ethical leadership in classroom management were discussed, and the power sources and characteristics of the teacher as an ethical leader were mentioned.

Findings, Conclusion and Discussion

Classroom Management

Classroom management; is the continuation of the necessary opportunities and processes for the realization of learning, by providing the learning order, environment and rules (Brophy, 1988). Teachers fulfill their classroom management duties by organizing educational processes and carrying out these processes in accordance with the purpose (Wragg, 2001). It can be said that the quality of education largely depends on the quality of classroom management (Demirel, 2017; Evertson & Harris, 1992; Senturk & Oral, 2008). It is known that teachers directly affect students' attitudes and behaviors in the classroom, and this effect leads to high academic participation in students and little tendency to undesirable behaviors (Baker, Clark, Maier & Viger, 2008; Greenwood, Horton & Utley, 2002). In this context, teachers who do not have effective classroom management skills may not be effective in the learning-teaching process,

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while having good classroom management knowledge and skills can enable teachers to cope with many difficulties. It can be said that the ability of students to be trained in the desired direction depends on the successful management of the classroom (Basar, 2014).

In order for teachers to demonstrate effective classroom management skills, they need to have the skills to provide an effective learning-teaching environment by using time efficiently, to put students' individual and social needs at the center, and to solve emerging problems in the most appropriate way. Classroom management knowledge and skills are one of the most important skills that teachers should have in order to create effective education and training environments (Charles, 1996; Levin & Nolan 1991; Wang, Haertel & Walberg, 1994). Classroom management is the whole of the activities that teachers do to create an environment that will facilitate and support academic and social/emotional learning (Evertson & Weinstein, 2006). In other words, classroom management is all the activities of the teacher in order to establish the classroom order and to ensure the participation and cooperation of the students in the lesson (Emmer & Stough, 2001). Classroom management can be defined as the multi-directional management of the educational life in the classroom like an orchestra (Lemlech, 2011). Classroom management is a systematic management approach that organizes and regulates the diversity and complexity of classrooms rather than being a teaching system (Tas, 2019).

Ensuring that students use time effectively and efficiently while working on educational activities, and minimizing the time that students spend by engaging in wasted or undesirable actions can be expressed as a good classroom management skill (Brophy, 1988). This will enable students to participate more actively in classroom activities and to spend more quality time. It can be said that the actions in the classroom affect the students and teachers in every aspect. It is known that poorly managed classrooms turn into problem centers and disciplinary problems are experienced a lot. It is stated that teachers who have effective classroom management strategies have fewer problems and more participation in the classroom (Emmer & Stough, 2001; Evertson, 1989). It can be said that teachers who do not have knowledge about classroom management cannot give their students the support they need. For this reason, it is important that teachers prefer to acquire knowledge in line with modern management approaches based on scientific data, rather than acquiring knowledge and skills on classroom management through trial and error (Yilmaz, 2006).

An effective classroom management that aims to reduce problematic student behaviors, increase student participation, prepare an environment that will facilitate academic and social-emotional learning, and ensure cooperation among students requires teachers to exhibit leadership behaviors in this sense. It is indispensable for leading teachers to have knowledge about administrative processes such as minimizing the problematic behaviors of students, ensuring healthy communication and interaction among students, making effective decisions, ensuring coordination, planning studies, organizing students in line with goals, and evaluating results.

Classroom management models

Classroom management models; traditional, reactive, precautionary, developmental and holistic (Erdogan, 2003; Kaya, 2003, Saritas, 2000; Yaka, 2006).

1. Traditional Model: In the traditional classroom management approach, education is teacher-centered. In classroom activities, the teacher is active and the students are passive. Teacher-student and student-student relations are structured and the teacher is the only authority (Babursah, 2014). In the traditional classroom management model; All activities such as classroom layout, interpersonal communication and interaction, human relations and time management are teacher-centered. The fact that the teacher is at the center of everything in the traditional classroom management model obliges the students to obey this authority unconditionally (Aydin, 2000). In this model, the rules and objectives are set by the teacher and it is obligatory to comply with the rules and to engage in activities in line with the determined purpose (Erdogan, 2003; Saritas, 2000). It can be said that this model creates oppressive teachers and unhappy students.

2. Reactive Model: In this model, it is aimed to change or eliminate the undesired behavior or situation that occurs in the classroom. The teacher's emphasis on the consequences of events rather than their causes, directing their reactions to more individuals, displaying a punitive understanding towards undesirable behaviors, emphasizing unconditional obedience to the rules that they have made as a goal, express the classroom management approach related to the reactive model (Senturk, 2006). This model is a classroom management model that aims to eliminate unwanted student behavior with reward-punishment activities. In this model, the main thing is that the teacher reacts to undesirable student behaviors. This model, which directly targets the individual and includes classical classroom management approaches, is criticized for limiting student-teacher communication and interaction and causing irreparable harm. The frequent use of this model by teachers indicates their low level of knowledge and skills in classroom management (Basar, 2014).

3. Precautionary Model: Precautionary model; It is a model based on the understanding of predicting, getting information beforehand, and preventing it before it occurs. In this model, which is based on the principle of creating a classroom order that can predict any situation that may cause problems in the classroom, the main aim is to prevent undesirable behaviors and situations before they occur (Basar, 2014). This model can also be expressed as a model of taking precautionary measures against problems that may arise in the classroom environment. The purpose of the precautionary model is not to allow problems to arise in the classroom, and to plan the classroom order and in-class relations accordingly. The problem here is to impose too many prohibitions in the name of taking precautions and to make the student unhappy by imposing too many restrictions. The fact that unforeseen situations can occur wherever the human element is present can sometimes render this model dysfunctional. At the same time, excessive precautionary anxiety can cause suffocation in the precautions (Senturk, 2006).

4. Developmental Model: This is a model that prioritizes consideration of students' developmental characteristics in the classroom management process (Basar, 2014). The main thing in this model is to set in-class rules and plan activities suitable for students' physical, mental and emotional development periods. It can be said that putting the developmental characteristics of students in the center of classroom management will increase academic success and reduce discipline problems. A teacher who has adopted this model is expected to plan and conduct his lesson according to the readiness level of the students. While determining the rules in the classroom, while assigning tasks and responsibilities to students, it is necessary to prioritize their developmental characteristics, to expect behaviors appropriate to their

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developmental level, and to consider individual development characteristics in various activities (Senturk, 2006). This model aims to implement the practices required by students' physical, emotional and experiential development levels in classroom management (Basar, 2014).

5. Holistic Model: This model, which is also called the system model, gives priority to the precautionary model and predicts that the teacher can use behaviors suitable for all models when necessary. To prevent undesirable behaviors and situations, the situations that cause them are eliminated. Students' developmental characteristics are taken into account (Basar, 2014). In this model, the teacher evaluates all models according to the contingency principle and determines their attitudes and behaviors. This model handles the class without abstracting it from its environment. A teacher who has adopted the holistic model approach is expected to show the behaviors based on the reactive model at the lowest level, and the behaviors based on the preventive and developmental model at the highest level (Senturk, 2006). A good classroom manager is a teacher who knows and uses certain classroom management techniques. The teacher's awareness and training in using these techniques changes the teacher's behavior, which in turn contributes to changing student behavior and making students successful (Marzano, Marzano & Pickering, 2009).

Basic Elements of Classroom Management

1. Teacher

A teacher who can increase the time students spend while working on academic activities and minimize the time they spend doing nothing or in inappropriate works can be defined as a teacher who has a good classroom management (Taş, 2019). Studies have shown that effective teachers have fewer behavioral problems and more participation in the classroom. It has been observed that teachers who do not use effective classroom management techniques adequately have difficulties in coping with students' behavioral problems and creating an efficient classroom environment (Yildiz, 2013).

2. Student

There is a wide variety of differences among students in social, economic and psychological aspects. Students are different from each other in many aspects such as the family's origin from village or city, income level, number of children, education of the family, values, beliefs, occupation of the parents, their attitudes towards the child and school, the value they attach to education, the gender of the child, the abilities, and the age of the physical characteristics. As a result of all these differences, it is natural that there are various differences in the behaviors, perspectives and ways of expressing themselves of the students who come to the classroom with different personality traits (Donmez, 2011). For this reason, it can be said that it is necessary for a good classroom management for teachers to know their students well in all aspects.

3. Family

People acquire some of the behaviors that make up their personalities in the family environment. Children learn the basic behaviors and values of the family in common family

life (Fidan, 2012). Among the elements outside the classroom, there are unwritten rules in the family, which is one of the most effective factors in student success, students' compliance with school rules, and their participation in social and cultural activities. While the family determines the boundaries of approved or disapproved behaviors, it also explains how these behaviors should be shown in which environments. The reward and punishment mechanism in the family also directs the behavior of the child. The family affects students' behavior in the classroom environment, learning situations and human relations. For this reason, teachers' close relationships with students' parents will make it easier for them to get to know their students and make sense of their behavior. This will ensure an effective classroom management. The positive relationship and cooperation between the teacher and the family will increase the success of the students, as well as increase the participation of the students in extracurricular social and cultural activities (Gelisl, 2011).

4. Manager

When class manager is mentioned, teachers come to mind first; because the teacher is the person who provides and maintains the appropriate environment for learning. The school administrator also ensures the provision and maintenance of the teaching environment. School administrators, especially teachers, should be accepted as classroom administrators (Erdogan, 2011). The main task of the school administrator is to manage the school with the understanding of continuous improvement. Meeting the physical needs of the school, increasing the motivation of teachers and students, developing human resources at school, improving school-society and school-parent relations are among the effective managerial behaviors. The school administrator is responsible for providing the school's human and material resources, using them appropriately and correctly, planning, supervising and evaluating all kinds of educational activities, ensuring cooperation and communication at school, and solving problems (Nural, 2002).

The management approach applied by the school administrator affects the classroom management approach of the teacher. In this sense, it can be said that the success of classroom management depends on the success of school management. Since the physical arrangement and capacity of the classroom, and the tools and equipment to be used are under the control and supervision of the school administration, the decisions to be taken by the school administration affect the classroom management.

5. School

School is a social organization created to achieve certain goals (Ulke, 2008). The social, economic, cultural and physical environment of the school, the number of students in the school and the size of the school, whether the school is in the city center or in the countryside, the administrative structure of the school, the socio-political situation in which the school is located, the level and status of the school, the financial inputs of the school, the school experience and attitudes of administrators and teachers. it is effective in creating an effective classroom environment and classroom management (Ozdemir, 2011b). Today, a good school is an institution that has suitable indoor and outdoor spaces, teachers who are experts in their profession and successful in human relations, has good relations with the society, and realizes the highest level of cooperation with the family by using all the opportunities provided by the society it is in (Oktay, 2007).

6. Peer group

In the classroom environment, students affect the behavior of both each other and their teachers. Most studies have found that many students conform to the norms of their peer group. These norms differ from the norms adopted by teachers. It is seen that students adopt the norms of being popular and athletic rather than school norms that support academic success (Demirbolat, 2011). The student's education, thoughts about the school, and behavior in the classroom affect other friends at school. Each class has one or more students who affect the other students in the class in a positive or negative way. In classes where the teacher cannot be a leader, the leader students affect the other students more (Erden, 2008). A good teacher-student relationship also affects other students' relationships. Students who have good relationships with their teachers also have a good relationship with other students, it becomes compatible (Ipek & Terzi, 2010).

Ethic

Ethics, which questions the qualitative conditions that make a behavior morally good (Pieper, 1999), deals with the moral problems of people in their individual and social life (Akarsu, 1998). The main subject of ethical debates is what evaluates human behavior and practices as morally right or wrong. Ethics, which does not aim to moralize or ideologize and aim to reach grounded results (Pieper, 1999), expresses the criteria of right and wrong about the past and present (Aydin, 2002). Ethics is a discipline of moral principles theory and philosophy that strives to realize a certain ideal of living, questions the era and society in which it lives, offers alternative values instead of existing values, clearly defines life norms, in short, makes life meaningful (Cevizci, 2002). As a philosophy discipline, ethics deals with morality, problems and judgments about morality, or moral problems and judgments (Frankena, 2007).

Ethics, which concerns moral action, behavior and judgment, is an important field of study of philosophy and science. Ethic; It is about right-wrong, good-bad, virtue-fault, and evaluating the results of actions and actions related to these concepts (Erdem, 2012). Ethics analyzes the status of moral terms and moral judgments used; It deals with the judgments behind moral attitudes (Gultekin, 2008). It also investigates the degree of influence of individual or social interests in ethical, moral decisions and judgments that seek answers to questions about how good, bad, right or wrong judgments are formed about people or their behaviors (Yilmaz, 2006). Professional ethics, on the other hand, is formed and protected by a professional group; forcing members of the profession to behave in a certain way; limiting the individual choices of members; exclude unprincipled members from the profession; It is a set of professional principles that regulate professional development and aim to protect service ideals (Aydin, 2012).

Ethics can be defined as a set of actions and moral principles accepted by a group of people or society. In other words, ethics is putting all actions and goals in their proper place, revealing what to do or not to do, what to want or not to want, what to have or not to have (Apaydin, 2009; Aydin, 2016; Karakutuk, 2002). Ethics, in general, recommends people what to do or what not to do; It can be defined as a set of values, principles and rules that enable to distinguish what is right and what is wrong.

Leadership

Leadership; The process of influencing and directing the behavior and activities of others without coercion, under certain conditions, in order to set personal and group goals and achieve set goals. A leader, on the other hand, is a person who directs and influences others to act in line with a certain purpose. The leader may have the power he uses while influencing the behavior of others, or he may have a charismatic aspect arising from some personal characteristics that are extremely valuable for the followers (Minaz, 2018a). The leader is a member of the group and helps develop ways of interaction that facilitate the achievement of shared goals by individuals. According to John Hemphill, group characteristics associated with leadership are the unity and togetherness that group members feel, and the sense of satisfaction they derive from group membership. Leadership is essentially a product of interaction, not status. The leadership structure cannot be predetermined. The uniqueness of group members, their interaction patterns, different goals and means, and different internal and external pressures on groups will create different leaders for each group. Someone who is perceived as a leader in one group may not be seen as a leader in another group. The leadership of the individual in the group depends on the perception of the group about that individual as well as the individual's perception of the leadership action and his own role (Demirbolat, 2001).

Ethical Leadership

Ethical leadership is a leadership style that displays management within the framework of normative conformity in personal activities and interpersonal relations and aims to increase such orientations by directing them to two-way communication, empowerment and moral thinking. In ethical leadership, "ethical characteristics" come to the fore from the leadership characteristics, and ethical leadership is related to "ethical values". Ethical leaders, in addition to drawing attention to ethical rules, give detailed explanations to their followers with examples. They help their employees to transform by setting an ethical example for their ethical behavior. Justice proceedings, the decisions they take and the punishments they give are observed and taken as an example by their followers (Erdem, 2015).

According to Ulug (2009), there is a need for honest, reliable ethical leaders who care about ethical principles and values in the light of universal references for the success of the institutional system. In terms of ethics-based management, the primary duty of the manager is to create an appropriate atmosphere of trust against the employees by whatever means. According to Arslantas & Dursun (2008), ethical leaders should exhibit morally exemplary behaviors, should not compromise on integrity and honesty, and there should be no inconsistency between their promises and practices.

The main purpose of leader behavior is to influence the activities of the members of the organization. Influencing the activities will reflect on the behavior of the employees and enable the organization to achieve its goals. The role behaviors of the leader, the strategies and tactics he follows affect the values, beliefs and behaviors of the followers as well as the achievement of the tasks in the organization and ensuring the harmony. The behavior of the leader and the strategies he follows become meaningful when they are perceived ethically correctly by the employees (Arslantas & Dursun, 2008).

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Harvey lists ten basic characteristics that guide the definition of ethical leadership. These characteristics that ethical leaders should have are (Yilmaz, 2006):

1. To create values and ethical awareness. Ethical leaders regularly articulate shared values, business principles, and ethical standards and ensure that these are understood, supported, and embraced.

2. Giving people responsibility. These leaders hold themselves and other people accountable for acting ethically.

3. To be an example to others. These leaders have the right to expect others to be honest because they are “one with their word”.

4. Making decisions within the framework of values. These leaders take care of others and their guiding principles in the decision-making process. They demonstrate their ethical values in everything they do.

5. To take care that the policies and practices are in harmony. This supports the rules and standards, values and ethics of leaders. When faced with an ethical dilemma, they resolve it quickly and without fear.

6. To provide education on values and ethics. These leaders devote time and resources to helping people gain the necessary confidence and complexity based on true beliefs and good behavior.

7. Paying attention to perceptions. These leaders pay attention to the feelings, opinions, and reactions of their colleagues, employees, statements, and everyone else within their sphere of influence.

8. To arrive at a stable and accelerating change. These leaders display many small paintings in many areas. The effects of a limit on compliance with ethical rules and values.

9. Recruit and promote people with ethical values. These leaders recruit people into the company and use their mission, vision, and values as decision criteria for promotion.

10. Ethical basic structures are not sufficient to show frameworks according to their structures, and to put forward the components of trust, respect, responsibility, justice and equality. Since we live in an age of constant change, these principles should be updated in accordance with the changes.

Teacher's Powers as an Ethical Leader

Based on the definitions made for leadership, it can be said that the leader's effectiveness in mobilizing the group and reaching the goal depends on his ability to use the "power" effectively, which emerges depending on the characteristics of the group. However, how and in what way the leader will use this power depends on the characteristics of the members who make up the organization. In this case, it can be said that the characteristics of the organization and the group directly affect the behavior of the leader and the use of power (Eraslan, 2004). Leadership is a dynamic behavior and there are many variables that affect leadership relationships. The

influence of the leader in an organization depends on the type of power the leader uses to influence other people (Ozkalp & Kirel, 2001).

1. Legal Power: Legal power is the right of the leader over the behavior of the followers due to the organizational hierarchy and the organizational position of the leader (Meydan, Dirik, & Eryilmaz, 2018). Regardless of the leader's personality, legal power arising from his hierarchical position in the organization refers to a subordinate's perception of the authority used by a leader who is elected or appointed to a certain position or position (Daft, 2004). It is the power that the law and school legislation gives to the teacher. The power to manage the classroom is legally vested in teachers. The teacher tries to influence the students by using this power. The teacher's excessive use of legal power may disturb the students and get the students' reaction. It causes students to distance themselves from it.

2. Charismatic Power: Charismatic power is the power that enables the followers to identify themselves with their leaders and to comply with the leader's wishes and demands (Elias, 2008). Charismatic power is the power that comes from personality traits such as self-confidence, courage, admiration, persuasion and motivation of the leader (Celik & Sunbul, 2008). Charismatic power stems from subordinates who have loyalty, loyalty and respect to their leaders and want to make them happy by fulfilling their leader's wishes (Yukl, 2002). The subordinate, who tries to identify with the leader, develops personal relationships such as loyalty and empathy, and fulfills his wishes because he loves the leader and thinks that he is a good person (Kaplan, 1964). The teacher uses this power to be liked by the students and by the teacher who is loved better to communicate with his students. The teacher maintains a friendly relationship with his students.

3. Specialization Strength: Expert power refers to the knowledge, skills and experiences of the leader on how the job should be done (Bakan & Buyukbese, 2010). Expert power relates to a subordinate's perception of the leader as experienced or knowledgeable. The basis of this perception is the presupposition that individuals are more knowledgeable and experienced than leaders themselves. The fact that teachers have a deep expertise in the subject increases their impact on students. The teacher, who can help the student learn enough, can influence his students more.

4. Reward and Coercive Power: The leader's rewarding and coercive power is related to the use of organizational resources and refers to the tangible or non-material rewards that the leader can distribute to the audience in response to the behaviors he deems appropriate, and the sanctions he can impose (Meydan, Dirik, & Eryilmaz, 2018). While rewarding power stems from a subordinate's perception that the leader can give rewards in return for displaying the expected behavior; coercive power arises from the subordinate's perception that the leader has the authority to punish him if he makes a mistake (Meydan & Polat, 2010). The teacher can make his leadership feel by using the power of reward and punishment in the classroom environment. Can use rewards and punishments in different ways without negatively affecting their students. The leader teacher is not the one who has one or more of these powers, but the teacher who can use all four powers effectively.

Qualities that a Teacher Should Have as an Ethical Leader

The concept of "ethics" in terms of the teaching profession with their students, the society they live in, and other professionals. the principles and rules that they must abide by in their relationships; occupational means the fulfillment of responsibilities. Other teachers that all members of the profession are teachers, It is a feature that gives them a privilege and gives them an important power. Teaching the one who makes his profession respectable in all societies and It can be said that it is this aspect that raises the position. this is so important in all the actions of members of a position in relation to their duties as well. and even act in accordance with ethical principles in their private lives. It turns out that they should do it (Obuz, 2009; Ozbek, 2003).

Teaching, where human relations are intense and ethical responsibilities can be defined as a profession. training task and teachers who have undertaken the responsibility of exemplary, but also with their lifestyles. are models. In this aspect, living what teachers teach It can be said that they are ideal examples. Also, the teaching profession a profession that undertakes the task of conveying only a set of information at the same time, it is aimed to add value to the young generations and It can be said that it is a profession that includes its duty (Senturk, 2009; Toprakci, Bozpolat & Buldur, 2010).

Respect people's opinions and thoughts, to be respectful, to tolerate differences, to be the of all students. Ethical leadership believe that it can happen, respect human rights, democratic take a stand, adopt universal values and contribute to its development. to internalize professional ethical values, to use information and communication technologies be aware of their legal and moral responsibilities to be, to respect the rights of the disabled, to be courteous, to and sharing their knowledge with their colleagues, being fair, and being consistent and honest in their actions ethical leadership in classroom management ethical behaviors expected from teachers who have taken on the role of are some. Solid and honest, based on ethical principles a society has only internalized ethical values and it can be possible with teachers who reflect it on their students.

Based on values in decision making and activities, to fulfill in line with the principles of honesty and integrity, protect and promote human rights, comply with national and local legislation to comply, to prevent the achievement of educational goals, to fight against behavior and regulations within the framework of ethical principles, political, social, religious or economic self-interest avoiding the behavior of students, colleagues and keeping the morale of other individuals high is ethical in classroom management can be expressed as leadership behaviors. The teacher, who is an ethical leader, personal, institutional, and societal issues while playing the ethical leadership role. must fulfill its responsibilities. The teacher as an ethical leader should know well the ethical principles and rules accepted in the society, this principle should be and align the rules with the ethical principles of the classroom.

Having a dynamic and effective personality being open, facilitating learning, updating oneself, being critical to think, to solve problems, to have the necessary knowledge and skills in the field to have, to be equipped with professional knowledge and skills, to think, to ask questions, to be sensitive, to love the profession, to the society and the country. to consider service as the basic principle, to strive to make the world beautiful, personality traits and sense

of responsibility required by the profession are the qualities that a teacher should have listed (Can, 2017; Eristi, 2008). Such important qualities a professional group that has the right to act in line with ethical principles, their attitudes and attitudes according to ethical norms, and they are expected to prioritize ethical values in their transactions.

1. Giving Confidence to the Group

The main point that leaders should not forget is to trust the people they work with. They cannot be expected to be motivated if the leader does not trust their group members or if the group members feel that they are not trusted. Education-teaching processes can be operated more effectively in classroom environments based on trust.

2. Developing a Vision

The leader must have a vision, be able to convey and share it with others. Where and why students go; They want to know what they are learning and why, and they dislike constantly changing goals and objectives. Teachers with vision attract attention with their classroom performances and take an active role in school improvement activities.

3. Being Brave

Creating effective solutions in critical moments is an important feature. This feature that distinguishes leaders from most followers, It is closely related to the courage of the leader. Leaders are cool and bold decision-making characteristics, organizational and individual goals is an important way to do it. As an ethical leader, the teacher to act by combining courage and calmness in classroom management, It can be considered as a result-taking leadership behavior.

4. Take risks

Leaders are able to achieve goals and solve problems effectively. They are people who take risks to solve it. The risk-taking ability of leaders in their success and increasing their influence on their followers. is an important factor. In classroom management of the teacher who is the leader, success and it is expected to take risks that maintain order. Your leader teacher taking risks affects students' academic success and socialization. provides important results. Leaders are people of critical decisions.

5. Become an expert

Leading teachers; specialist in business and transactions related to their profession are people who are. One of the most distinctive features of leaders is their have a good command of their fields of activity, have a high level of knowledge about the work they do knowledge and good general knowledge. Teaching as a specialized profession in legal texts it is this expertise power that underlies the definition of can be said. The leader teacher teaches his students in the classroom environment as an expert. precedes expert knowledge with his attitudes and behaviors plan will increase its impact on students.

6. Emphasizing Differences

Leader teachers give importance to the differences of students and they support you in every way. As an ethical leader, the teacher an understanding of classroom management in which the student can express himself comfortably exhibits and creates a high morale class climate. Trying to understand each student without marginalizing and accepting valuable is an ethical leader's attitude.

7. Leveling up/Easing

Ethical leaders want to be understood by their followers. Viewers to be understood correctly, to simplify the work and operations, to choose simpler expressions in the narration and especially to the addressed it requires knowing the audience well as a level of understanding. Teacher, both in classroom management and course topics and classroom come down to the level in explaining the rules, choose understandable sentences, easy methods and techniques should be applied. Your leader teacher the ability to level up and simplify it provides classroom management.

Ethical Leadership in Classroom Management

The teacher is considered the ethical leader of the classroom environment, and the influence of the teacher on his students stems from his leadership qualities. While ethical behaviors have positive effects on the audience, unethical behaviors have negative effects on the audience. It creates a bad model for the followers of unethical behaviors of the leaders (Brawn & Trevino, 2006). In this case, it is imperative that teachers, who have an ethical leadership role in the classroom and are responsible for being a model for students at every opportunity, pay maximum attention to ethical principles. When the principles of teaching professional ethics are examined in general, a picture of an educator who has adopted the features and universal values that the society accepts at a high level emerges. Performance in teacher competencies also includes similar values. It is the determinant of success and effectiveness in education in general and in values education in particular that all teachers transform the values included in the principles of teaching professional ethics and teacher competencies into practice in a way to be a model for students/children in school and out-of-school environments. In summary, teachers who have developed their professional competencies and practiced the ethical principles of the teaching profession are described as effective and successful teachers (Sen, 2011).

Virtues such as being truthful and respectful, adopting social norms, being helpful, and not doing injustice are among the ethical values desired by all societies (Yorukoglu, 2016). Teachers, who have the power to develop rules, solve problems, have discussions, respect students, give them responsibility, teach basic ethical values such as being a good listener, democracy and self-confidence (Kirschenbaum, 1995), have an undeniable relay in conveying ethical values. Valuing the opinions and thoughts of others, respecting differences, protecting children's rights, respecting human rights, adopting social ethical values, knowing and fulfilling legal and moral responsibilities, being fair, being consistent in their words and behaviors, being honest. It is known that the most important task in transferring principles and values to future generations is in educational institutions and teachers.

Leader teachers have undertaken an important task/responsibility such as realizing the education policies of the state and the country's far and near educational goals. Duties, authorities and responsibilities of teachers; determined on the basis of laws, statutes, regulations, directives, circulars, programs and instructions. of teachers; It will be an inevitable behavior of educators to take into account professional ethical principles and rules in proportion to legal regulations and government policies while fulfilling their duties of training, enlightenment, regulation and supervision. Since the main purpose of ethics education is to ensure that the individual obeys the rules of the society he is a member of, to convey the basic principles of reaching an ideal society to the individual and to solve the problems that have arisen as a result of the deviation in ethical values, it can be stated that a good ethics education will be a good solution. It can be said that the first degree architects of this solution are the leading teachers who lead their classrooms with ethical principles and values.

Predetermined laws, statutes, regulations, directives, etc. Written regulations such as educational institutions may sometimes be insufficient in the process of fulfilling individual and social goals. In cases where the legal legislation is left open or insufficient, the ethical values of the teacher can function as an important fulcrum in education management in general and classroom management in particular. Since management is not only a process with technical, legal, political and financial dimensions, but also an activity with an ethical dimension (Efil, 2007), it can be seen that the behavior or decisions of the teacher, who is the leader of classroom management, are affected by moral tendencies/judgments. An effective ethical culture in the classroom should be created by the teacher in order for the school to continue without interruption, for the moral codes approved by the society to be transferred to the students and for the students to gain ethical values. In order for the teacher to create a culture that prioritizes ethical values in the classroom, it is inevitable that all attitudes and behaviors exhibited by the teacher comply with ethical principles. It is known that one of the most important factors that reduces the performance of students and spoils their morale is the suspicion that teachers are honest and impartial, in other words, the perception that the teacher acts against ethical principles in classroom management (Minaz, 2018b).

If the teacher values the opinions of the students, is open to criticism, approaches differences with tolerance, empathizes with the students, does not judge them and listens to them, they can put ethical principles at the center of classroom management. A teacher's respect for human rights, being transparent and sharing, not compromising honesty and truthfulness in their attitudes and behaviors can make them perceived as an ethical leader by the students.

While the new conditions of our world, which has entered a serious change and transformation process, increase the need for ethics education; The desire of nations to transfer their ethical values to new generations also causes us to present ethics education as an important requirement. It is the common responsibility of the family, school and society to educate children, who will be a dynamic member of the society in the future, in accordance with the rules adopted by the society (Turan & Ilkay, 2016). It is understood that situations such as increasing violence tendency, rebellion, drug addiction, loss of sense of duty and awareness of individual and social responsibility are increasing. Therefore, it is vital that schools take part in this sense for children who have not received adequate ethical education from their families. Therefore, it is impossible to talk about an education that does not undertake the task of conveying ethical values (Lickona, 1996). Therefore, education systems should clearly reveal

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the right and wrong, values, principles, norms, attitudes and behaviors that are approved and disapproved by the society, and provide individuals with the right methods and techniques.

In addition to the cognitive development of people, transferring personal and social values can be counted among the most important goals of educational activities (Gultekin, 2007). Considering the fact that the future of societies will be shaped by well-educated people with character and adherence to ethical principles, and the fact that people with these characteristics cannot grow up on their own; Schools have important duties in order to raise well-educated, characterful and moral individuals (Eksi, 2003). Schools that contribute to the integration process of individuals with the society they live in (Gultekin, 2007) are not expected to be a spectator to the ethical problems that arise in the society, but to affect the values, social behaviors and characters of the new generation and thus contribute to the society having the desired ethical values (Lickona, 1993).

Effective classrooms make up an effective school. It is the teachers who have the leadership qualities that make the classes effective. The climate and organizational structure that teachers create in their classrooms affect the whole school. Developing the leadership role of the teacher will increase the quality of school management. Because the teacher leader will participate in the decision-making process more consciously and will contribute to the organizational change of the school (Celik, 2012). The informal dimension of the teacher's leadership behavior carries more weight than the formal dimension. As an informal leader, the teacher also tries to play roles such as voluntarily participating in school improvement projects, dealing specifically with students' problems, and developing new ideas for school improvement (Leithwood, Jantzi & Steinbach, 1999).

Leader teachers are people who are open to development and change. These teachers, with their attitudes and behaviors, add movement to the institution they are in, and become the accelerator of development and change. Leader teachers who have adopted ethical principles take ethical principles and values as reference in their personal and institutional attitudes and behaviors. Rules based on ethical principles work in the classrooms of these teachers, and their students are in communication and coordination based on ethical principles. The teacher's prioritizing universal ethical principles in his attitudes and behaviors in the classroom allows him to be accepted as an ethical leader by the students. This acceptance accelerates the process of achieving the purpose of classroom activities.

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Ethical Declaration and Committee Approval

In this research, the principles of scientific research and publication ethics were followed. This study is not a study conducted with qualitative or quantitative approaches that requires data collection from participants using survey, interview, focus group work, observation, experiment, interview techniques, since it is not a study in which humans and animals (including material/data) are used for experimental or other scientific purposes, and people and since there is no clinical study on animals, it does not require ethical committee approval.

